

Studies in the Synthesis of Coumarino- α -pyrones and Furocoumarins Part XV¹ : Kostanecki-Robinson Acylation of *o*-Hydroxy Acylcoumarins

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Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation of 7-hydroxy-6-benzoyl-8-methyl-4-phenylcoumarin, 7-hydroxy-6-benzoyl-8-methylcoumarin and 4-hydroxy-3-benzoyl-7,8-benzocoumarin gave the corresponding coumarino- α -pyrone derivatives while 3-chloro-4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetylcoumarin and 4-hydroxy-3-propionyl-7,8-benzocoumarin gave the corresponding coumarino- γ -pyrone derivatives. The structures of the compounds (VIIIa) and (VIIIb) obtained by Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation of 7-hydroxy-8-propionylcoumarin and 7-hydroxy-8-butyrylcoumarin are revised on the basis of I.R. Spectra.

In continuation of our work on the synthesis of coumarino- α -pyrones² by Kostanecki-Robinson reaction on 7-hydroxy-6-acylcoumarins, we report here some of our further studies on the above reaction. These *o*-hydroxy acylcoumarins were prepared either by Fries migration of the corresponding acyloxy or aryloxy derivatives or by Friedel-Crafts acylation.

Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation of 7-hydroxy-6-benzoyl-8-methyl-4-phenylcoumarin³ gave a mixture of two compounds. The separation of the mixture was affected by warming the mixture with ethanol. Compound (Ia) was soluble in ethanol while the residue (IIa) crystallised from acetic acid. The compound was found to be 7-acetoxy-6-benzoyl-8-methyl-4-phenylcoumarin (Ia) by mixed m.p. determination with its authentic sample. It was deacetylated to the original ketone by the action of 60% sulphuric acid. The compound (IIa) was assigned 10-methyl-4,6-diphenyl-2,8-dioxo-2H,8H-pyrano(3,2-g)benzopyran structure.

7-Hydroxy-6-benzoyl-8-methylcoumarin⁴ when subjected to Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation under similar experimental conditions gave the corresponding 7-acetoxy-6-benzoyl-8-methylcoumarin (Ib) and 10-methyl-4-phenyl-2,8-dioxo-2H,8H-pyrano (3,2-g) benzopyran (IIb).

Pechmann condensation of 4-hydroxy-7,8-benzocoumarin⁵ (IIIa) with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of nitrobenzene and anhydrous aluminium chloride gave 4-methyl-2,5-dioxo-2H,5H-pyrano (3,2-c) benzo(h)benzopyran (IVa), whereas Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation of 4-hydroxy-3-benzoyl-7,8-benzocoumarin (IIIc) and 4-hydroxy-3-propionyl-7,8-benzocoumarin (IIId) gave 4-phenyl-2,5-dioxo-2H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c)benzo(h)benzopyran (IVb) and 2,3-dimethyl-4,5-dioxo-4H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c)benzo(h)benzopyran (V) respectively. Compound (IIIc) was obtained by benzoylation followed by Fries migration of (IIIa) whereas (IIId) was obtained by Friedel-Crafts propionylation of (IIIa).

3-Chloro-4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetylcoumarin on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation gave 2,8-dimethyl-3-acetyl-7-chloro-4,6-dioxo-4H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (VI). Deacetylation of (VI) with 5% sodium carbonate solution resulted in simultaneous opening of the γ -pyrone ring and the contraction of α -pyrone ring to furan ring, to afford 3-methyl-6-hydroxy-7-acetylbenzofuran (VII)⁶. Deacetylation of (VI) with 60% sulphuric acid met with failure.

Shah and Contractor⁷ carried out Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation of 7-hydroxy-8-propionylcoumarin and 7-hydroxy-8-butyrylcoumarin and obtained products to which they assigned 4-ethyl-2,6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (VIIIa), m.p. 276° and 4-propyl-2,6-dioxo-2H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (VIIIb) m.p. 240° structures. In the normal course of reaction, Kostanecki-Robinson reaction gives γ -pyrones, except in the case of *o*-hydroxy-benzophenone, where α -pyrone is formed. The work was, therefore, repeated and it was found that under similar experimental conditions, compounds (IXa), m.p. 276° and (IXb), m.p. 243° were obtained instead of (VIIIa) and (VIIIb). The I.R. Spectra of (IXa) and (IXb) showed two bands in the carbonyl region, 1750 cm^{-1} (lactone) and 1660 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl). This is incompatible with the structures (VIIIa) and (VIIIb) assigned by Shah and Contractor.

Further, the same authors reported that 7-hydroxy-8-propionylcoumarin and 7-hydroxy-8-butyrylcoumarin when subjected to Kostanecki-Robinson reaction using sodium phenyl acetate and acetic anhydride, the compounds (VIIIc), m.p. 276° and (VIId), m.p. 230° were obtained. We repeated the work and identified the products as (IXa) and (IXb). Hence it appears that during the reaction, no phenyl acetylation has taken place.

EXPERIMENTAL

10-Methyl-4,6-diphenyl-2,8-dioxo-2H,8H-pyrano(3,2-g) benzopyran (IIa): A mixture of 7-hydroxy-6-benzoyl-8-methyl-4-phenylcoumarin (1 g.), acetic anhydride (10 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (4 g.) was heated at 190° in an oil bath for 10 hr. The reaction mixture, after cooling, was added to crushed ice. The separated product was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The t.l.c. of the product showed it to be the mixture of two compounds. The mixture was refluxed with alcohol and filtered. The residue crystallised from acetic acid and had m.p. 284° (yield 0.4 g.) The compound did not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 78.86; H, 4.11. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 78.94; H, 4.21%).

7-Acetoxy-6-benzoyl-8-methyl-4-phenylcoumarin (Ia): The alcoholic mother liquor was concentrated. On cooling, the crystals of (Ia) were deposited, which after filtration, recrystallised from alcohol and had m.p. 164°. (Yield; 0.2 g.). (Found: C, 75.60; H, 4.66. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 75.47; H, 4.52%).

10-Methyl-4-phenyl-2,8-dioxo-2H,8H-pyrano(3,2-g) benzopyran (IIb): A mixture of 7-hydroxy-6-benzoyl-8-methylcoumarin (1 g.), acetic anhydride (10 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (4 g.) was heated at 180° in an oil bath for 8 hr. Working up the reaction mixture as described above, the product crystallised from acetic acid and had m.p. 250°.

(yield; 0.4 g.). The compound did not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 74.87; H, 3.95. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 74.99; H, 3.94%).

7-Acetoxy-6-benzoyl-8-methylcoumarin (Ib) : Alcoholic mother liquor was concentrated and the product after filtration, recrystallised from alcohol and had m.p. 154° (yield; 0.15 g.). (Found : C, 70.50; H, 4.36. $C_{19}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 70.79; H, 4.34%).

4-Methyl-2,5-dioxo-2H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c)benzo(h) benzopyran (IVa) : A mixture of 4-hydroxy-7,8-benzocoumarin (2 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (2 ml.) was added to a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (5 g.) in nitrobenzene (15 ml.) and it was heated at 130° in an oil bath for 4 hr. After cooling, it was decomposed with conc. hydrochloric acid containing pieces of ice. The reaction mixture was steam distilled to remove nitrobenzene. The separated product was filtered and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove original compound. It crystallised from acetic acid and had m.p. 281° (yield; 1 g.). (Found : C, 73.20; H, 3.77. $C_{17}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 73.38; H, 3.59%).

4-Benzoyloxy-7,8-benzocoumarin (IIIb) : To a solution of 4-hydroxy-7,8-benzocoumarin (2 g.) in pyridine (15 ml.) and piperidine (2-3 drops), benzoyl chloride (4 ml.) was slowly added with constant shaking at 0°. The reaction mixture was kept for 15 min. in an ice bath and then was added to conc. hydrochloric acid (50 ml.) containing ice pieces. The separated product was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove original compound and dried. It crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether and has m.p. 186° (yield; 5 g.). (Found : C, 75.91; H, 3.75. $C_{20}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 75.95; H, 3.97%).

4-Hydroxy-3-benzoyl-7,8-benzocoumarin (IIIc) : An intimate mixture of 4-benzoyloxy-7,8-benzocoumarin (2 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (8 g.) was heated at 150° in an oil bath for 2 hr. The mixture was decomposed with conc. hydrochloric acid (50 ml.) containing ice pieces. The separated product was filtered and dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution. It was filtered and the filtrate on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave the pure product. The product was dried and dissolved in benzene and the solution was run over a short column of alumina. The product was eluted with benzene and the residue after evaporation of solvent, crystallised from acetic acid and has m.p. 183° (yield; 1.4 g.). The compound developed characteristic purple colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 75.70; H, 3.72. $C_{20}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 75.95; H, 3.97%).

4-Phenyl-2,5-diox-2H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c)benzo(h)benzopyran (IVb) : A mixture of 4-hydroxy-3-benzoyl-7,8-benzocoumarin (1 g.), acetic anhydride (8 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (4 g.) was heated at 180° in an oil bath for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice and the separated product was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and dried. It was dissolved in chloroform and the solution was run over a short column of alumina. The product was eluted with chloroform. After the evaporation of solvent, the residue crystallised from acetic acid and had m.p. 225° (yield; 0.6 g.). The compound did not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 77.64; H, 3.57. $C_{22}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 77.64; H, 3.53%).

4-Hydroxy-3-propionyl-7,8-benzocoumarin (IIIId) : A mixture of 4-hydroxy-7,8-benzocoumarin (2 g.), propionic acid (10 ml.) and phosphorus oxychloride (6 ml.) was gently refluxed

on a sand bath for 2 hr. The mixture was poured into crushed ice and the separated product filtered, washed with water and dried. It was dissolved in benzene and the solution was run over a short column of alumina. The product was eluted with benzene and finally crystallised from acetic acid and had m.p. 162° (yield; 1.4 g.). The compound developed characteristic purple colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 71.40; H, 4.31. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.64; H, 4.48%).

2,3-Dimethyl-4,5-dioxo-4H,5H-pyrano(3,2-c)benzo(h)benzopyran (V) : A mixture of 4-hydroxy-3-propionyl-7,8-benzocoumarin (1 g.), acetic anhydride (8 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (4 g.) was heated at 190° in an oil bath for 10 hr. Working up as described earlier and running its chloroform solution over alumina, the product crystallised from acetic acid and had m.p. 308° (yield; 0.5 g.). The compound did not develop any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 73.72; H, 4.08. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 73.98; H, 4.11%).

2,8-Dimethyl-3-acetyl-7-chloro-4,6-dioxo-4H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (VI) : A mixture of 3-chloro-4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetylcoumarin (1 g.), acetic anhydride (8 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (3 g.) was heated at 170° in an oil bath for 8 hr. After cooling, the reaction mixture was filtered, washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and crystallised from acetic acid and had m.p. 281° (yield; 0.4 g.). (Found : C, 61.54; H, 3.20; Cl, 10.93. $C_{16}H_{10}O_5Cl$ requires C, 61.80; H, 3.10; Cl, 11.10%).

2,3-Dimethyl-4,6-dioxo-4H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (IXa) A mixture of 7-hydroxy-8-propionylcoumarin (1 g.), acetic anhydride (8 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (8 g.) was heated at 170° in an oil bath for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove original compound. It crystallised from acetic acid and had m.p. 276° (lit.⁷ m.p. 276°) (yield; 0.6 g.). (Found : C, 69.10; H, 3.96. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 69.42; H, 4.12%).

2-Methyl-3-ethyl-4,6-dioxo-4H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran (IXb) : A mixture of 7-hydroxy-8-butyrylcoumarin (1 g.), acetic anhydride (10 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (3 g.) was heated at 170° in an oil bath for 10 hr. Working up as above, the product crystallised from acetic acid and had m.p. 243° (lit.⁷ m.p. 240°) (yield; 0.6 g.). (Found : C, 70.09; H, 4.65. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 70.37; H, 4.69%).

2,3-Dimethyl-4,8-dioxo-4H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran : 7-Hydroxy-8-propionylcoumarin (1 g.), acetic anhydride (8 ml.) and sodium phenylacetate (3 g.) was heated at 170° in an oil bath for 8 hr. After usual work up the compound crystallised from acetone and had m.p. 278° (lit.⁷ m.p. 275°); mixed m.p. with (IXa) did not depress. I.R. Spectrum and microanalysis of this compound were in agreement with that of (IXa). (Found : C, 69.30; H, 4.00. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 69.42; H, 4.12%).

2-Methyl-3-ethyl-4,6-dioxo-4H,6H-pyrano(2,3-h)benzopyran : A mixture of 7-hydroxy-8-butyrylcoumarin (1 g.), acetic anhydride (8 ml.) and sodium phenylacetate (3 g.) was heated at 170° in an oil bath for 8 hr. After usual work up the product crystallised from acetone and had m.p. 245° (lit.⁷ m.p. 230°), mixed m.p. with (IXb) did not depress. I.R. Spectrum

and microanalysis of this compound were in agreement with (IXb). (Found : C, 70.21; H, 4.58. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 70.37; H, 4.69%).

a : $R = C_6H_5$

b : $R = H$

I

a : $R = C_6H_5$

b : $R = H$

II

a : $R = R_1 = H$

b : $R = H$; $R_1 = COC_6H_5$

c : $R = COC_6H_5$; $R_1 = H$

d : $R = COCH_2CH_3$; $R_1 = H$

III

a : $R = CH_3$

b : $R = C_6H_5$

IV

a : $R = H$; $R_1 = C_2H_5$

b : $R = H$; $R_1 = C_3H_7$

c : $R = C_6H_5$; $R_1 = C_2H_5$

d : $R = C_6H_5$; $R_1 = C_3H_7$

VIII

a : $R = R_1 = CH_3$

b : $R = CH_3$; $R_1 = C_2H_5$

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R E F E R E N C E S

1. Part XIV. N. H. Pardhanani and K. N. Trivedi, (Communicated).
2. N. H. Pardhanani, M. G. Parekh and K. N. Trivedi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 36.
3. N. H. Pardhanani, M. G. Parekh and K. N. Trivedi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 1014.
4. N. H. Pardhanani and K. N. Trivedi, *J. Inst. Chem.*, 1970, **42**, 153.
5. N. Anand and K. Vankataraman, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1948, **28A**, 151.
6. D. B. Limaye and N. R. Sethe, *Rasayanam.*, 1936, **1**, 48; *Chem. Abs.*, 1937, **31**, 2212.
7. D. N. Shah and S. J. Contractor, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 505.